

Terpenoids : Part XXXIV. A New Synthesis of (\pm) Dihydrocarvone

O. P. Vig, Om Parkash Chugh and Khushi Lall Matta

Dihydrocarvone, a monocyclic monoterpene ketone, occurs in nature in the laevo rotatory form.¹ The formulation (I) has been established for this ketone on the basis of physical and chemical evidence.

Its preparation has been reported from naturally occurring carvone.² Various syntheses of dl. dihydrocarvone have been achieved in this laboratory.³⁻⁵ However, in the present studies, a new synthesis of this ketone has been accomplished by making use of an elegant approach investigated by House and coworkers,⁶ for the introduction of isopropenyl group. Thus 6-methyl- Δ^2 -cyclohexenone⁷(II) when submitted to Grignard reaction with isopropenyl magnesium bromide, in the presence of catalytic amount of cuprous iodide, affords the title compound in 60% yield.

The synthetic ketone was characterised through I.R. spectrum and melting points of its 2,4- dinitrophenylhydrazone, oxime and semicarbazone derivatives.

1. A. R. Pinder, "The Chemistry of the terpenes, (Chapman and Hall Ltd. London), (1960), p. 74.
2. J. L. Simonsen, "The Terpenes", Vol. I (The University Press, Cambridge), 1947, 351.
3. O. P. Vig., *J. Gen. Org. Chem.*, U.S.S.R., 1961, **31**, 669.
4. O. P. Vig, S.D. Sharma, Suresh Chander and Inder Raj, *Indian, J. Chem.*, 1965, **3**, 425.
5. O. P. Vig., Amrik Lal and K. L. Matta, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.* (accepted).
6. H. O. House, R. A. Latham and C. D. Slater, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1966, **31**, 2667.
7. G. Stork and W. N. White, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **78**, 4605.

EXPERIMENTAL

Melting and boiling points are uncorrected. Microanalysis by Mr. B. N. Anand, Microanalyst of our Department. I.R. absorption spectrum was recorded on Perkin-Elmer infracord spectrometer with sodium chloride optics using a thin liquid film.

2-Methyl-5-isopropenyl-cyclohexanone (*dihydrocarvone*) I. To magnesium (1.22 g.) in tetrahydrofuran (35 ml.) and a crystal of iodine was added 2-Bromo-propene (8.3 g.) in tetrahydrofuran (20 ml.) over a period of 1 hr. The reaction mixture was then refluxed for 15 minutes in order to dissolve magnesium completely. The Grignard reagent so prepared was diluted with 30 ml. of tetrahydrofuran and cooled to 0°. Freshly prepared anhydrous cuprous iodide (0.5 g.) was added followed by the dropwise addition of 2.63 g. of 6-methyl- Δ^2 -cyclohexenone in tetrahydrofuran (15 ml.), with stirring, over a period of 15 minutes. The stirring was further continued for one additional hour. The reaction mixture was then added to the cold aqueous solution of ammonia and ammonium chloride and the organic layer was separated. The aqueous phase was extracted with ether and the combined organic extract was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the solvent expelled. Distillation of the residue afforded 2-methyl-5-isopropenylcyclohexanone (\pm Dihydrocarvone), in 60% yield, (2.0 g.), b.p. 88-90/5-6 mm. η^{25}_D 1.4700, lit.² η°_D 1.4710. Found C, 79.10; H, 10.29. Calc. for $C_{10}H_{16}O$, C, 78.95; H, 10.53%.

I.R. spectrum peaks: 1720 ($-C=O$), 1645, and 895 cm^{-1} and $\left(\begin{array}{l} R_1 \\ R \end{array} \right) > C=CH_2$.

The 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone prepared by sulphuric acid method 2,4-method in cold was crystallised from absolute ethanol, m.p. 155°. (Found N, 17.10. Calc. for $C_{16}H_{20}N_4O_4$, N, 16.87%).

The oxime prepared by the usual method and crystallised from ethanol melts at 115.5° (lit.² reports m.p. 115.16°) Found N, 8.75. Calc. for $C_{10}H_{17}NO$, N, 8.38%.

The semicarbazone derivative of the synthetic product (I), melted at 166-67° (from methanol), Lit.⁸ reports m.p. 168°. Found N, 19.95. Calc. for $C_{11}H_{19}N_3O$, N, 20.09.

DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
PANJAB UNIVERSITY,
CHANDIGARH-14.

Received, March 30, 1968.